

Flow Injection Potentiometry of Bromide Ions in Sea Water

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The advantages of the bromide ion selective electrode in flow injection systems are pretty visible when analysing bromide in sea water at the average ratio of 1000. $\text{Br}^-/\text{Cl}^- = 3.95$ on $32-52 \text{ mg dm}^{-3}$ bromide level. Direct flow injection potentiometry was applied without pretreating the sample. The matrix effect of high chloride concentration was simply removed while calibrating the electrode by means of sodium chloride. The results obtained agree well with those recommended in literature with coefficient of variation $< 1\%$ and the simplified system compares favourably with spectrophotometric methods

THE ion-selective electrodes (ISE) are frequently applied in oceanographic explorations^{1,2}. However a great part of the known electrodes cannot be used owing to their insufficient selectivity and sensitivity. Br^- -ISE also belongs to this group³ due to the hindering influence of the chloride and iodide ions. Savenko³ adduced data for determining Br^- in sea water with the help of conventional potentiometry. However our previous experiments⁴ and literature data^{5,6} indicate that in this case the analysis is not correct enough due to constant drift of the potential caused by the high chloride concentration. In this case, the influence of iodide ions, which in sea water are of the order of $10^{-6} - 10^{-5} \text{ M}$, should not be neglected⁷. The advantages offered by flow injection potentiometry (FIP) with regard to improving the functions of ISE are well-known^{4,8-10}. On the basis of the above considerations, the authors aimed at studying the possibility of using Br^- -ISE under conditions of FIP, with a view to its application in determining Br^- in sea water.

Experimental

Apparatus: The block-schemes of the flow injection system and flow cells used are shown in Fig. 1. The system consists of a multichannel peristaltic pump (Ismatec), two-position injector valve with two loops of equal volume and mV/pH-meter (OP-208 Radelkis), connected to a recorder polarograph (OH-105, Radelkis) for signal recording. The electrode pair consists of Br^- -ISE (Citrur) and a saturated calomel as reference electrode (Radelkis). The two-channel flow injection system permits the elimination of eventual differences of the physico-chemical properties between the calibration and

analysed solution (ionic strength, viscosity, etc.). The main part of the experiment was performed with the cell shown Fig. 1b and part of the sea water analyses with the cell in Fig. 1c and 'wall-jet' cell¹¹.

Fig 1 Flow injection system: (1) peristaltic pump, (2) injector, (3) mV/pH-meter, (4) recorder, (5) detector cell, (6) Br^- -ISE, (7) reference electrode, (8) strip of filter paper, (9) perspex cup, (10) porous membrane.

All reagents (NaBr, NaCl, NaI, NaNO₃) used were of reagent grade. The solutions were prepared with double-distilled water. The flow carrier solution was degassed with the help of a water pump.

Calibration : The calibration was performed in all cases with 5 separate calibrating solutions in measuring flasks of 100.00 ml, containing a mixture of 10, 20, 40, 70 and 100 ppm bromide and 0.1 M chloride. A 100 μl of the calibrating solution was injected into the flow carrier (0.7 M NaNO₃). The analytical signals obtained were proportional to the logarithm of the bromide concentration and were treated after the method of regression analysis.

Selectivity : The quantitative evaluation of the selectivity of the bromide membrane in relation to chloride and iodide ions presented by the selectivity coefficients $K_{Br/Cl}^{Pot}$ and $K_{Br/I}^{Pot}$, were calculated by the method of separate solutions².

Methods of flow injection potentiometry of Br⁻ in sea water : A system optimised for this analytical task was used (Table 1). The flow carrier was 0.7 M NaNO₃ with a velocity of 2 ml min⁻¹ in both the channels. The calibrating solutions were 5 in number containing bromide ions from 10 to 100 ppm and a constant concentration of chloride ions (0.2 or 0.15 M) depending on the chlorides in the analysed samples. The volume of the injected sample of calibrating solution and sea water was 100 μl. It may be noted that the determination of chlorides in a particular sample of sea water was performed titrimetrically^{1,2}.

TABLE 1—STUDY ON THE INFLUENCE OF CERTAIN PARAMETERS WITH A VIEW TO OPTIMISING THE SYSTEM

Sl. no.	Parameters	Area alteration	Optimum
1.	Sample volume (μl)	25–150	100
2.	Velocity of the flow carrier (both channels) (ml min ⁻¹)	0.6–6.2	2.0
3.	Bromide added to the flow carrier (ppm)	0–8	1
4.	Chloride added to flow carrier (mM)	0–10	0

Results and Discussion

Detailed study was made on the influence of the parameters of the flow injection system on the sensitivity and selectivity of the signal.

Sample dispersion : The observation shows that the selectivity of ISE in conditions of FIP is different from that of the conventional potentiometry^{4,13}. Responsible for this are the hydrodynamic conditions in the flow system, the general criterion of which is the dispersion of the sample *D*. It was shown in our previous study that by increasing the dispersion of the sample, the selectivity coefficients approached unity⁴.

By increasing the dispersion of the sample, the selectivity of the bromide membrane in the presence

of iodide is improved, while the same membrane in the presence of chloride maintains its selectivity to a given value of *D*.

These experimental data enable us to assume that the use of Br⁻-ISE in FIP of sea water must be carried out on a system with low dispersion (≈4). However it must be remembered that at dispersion of the sample smaller than 2, the speed of analysis is three times smaller than that at dispersion 4 as a result of increase of temporary drift of the base line. On the basis of these considerations, a sensible compromise is to carry out analysis of Br⁻ in sea water at dispersion of *ca* 4. In these conditions (in comparison with conventional potentiometry), the kinetic discrimination of iodide ion increases the selectivity of Br⁻ membrane 1000 times, while the selectivity of electrode in presence of chloride ions remains unchanged.

Presence of bromide in the flow carrier : The addition of a potential-determining ion in the flow carrier has been recently practiced and widely discussed in the literature^{14,15}. In this way, the analysis rate is increased due to the reduced time for obtaining analytical signals (Fig. 2A–D). At the same time, height of the signals lowers but not the

Fig. 2. Influence of Br⁻ and Cl⁻ in flow carrier (0.7 M NaNO₃) on the signal of bromide selective electrode. Each injected sample is a mixture of 100 mM Cl⁻ and Br⁻ whose concentration is indicated over the respective signal in ppm. The added bromide ions in the flow carrier are: (A) 0.0, (B) 0.08, (C) 0.8 and (D) 8.0 ppm; the carrier flow (E) is a mixture of 0.7 M NaNO₃ + 5 mM KCl. The velocity of the flow carrier = 2.0 ml min⁻¹ (for both flows, Fig. 1); volume of the injected sample = 100 μl.

gradient of the electrode function. This is well-illustrated in Fig. 3, where calibration curves are showed under different conditions in absence and in presence of chloride ions in the calibrating solutions and with varying bromide concentrations in the flow carrier.

Fig. 4 gives the calculated values of $K_{Br/Cl}^{Pot}$ of the experimental material given in Fig. 3. It may be

Fig. 3. Calibration curves of Br⁻-ISE : (a) in presence of 0.1 M Cl⁻. Carrier flow (for a and b) is 0.7 M NaNO₃ and with addition of Br⁻ whose concentration (from 0 to 8.0 ppm) is designated on the calibration curves. The injected volume is 100 μl and velocity of the flow carrier in both channels (Fig. 1) is 2.0 ml min⁻¹; (b) pure bromide solutions.

seen that selectivity of the electrode improves up to five times with an increase in Br⁻ concentration in the flow carrier from 0 to 8 ppm. The improved selectivity is well-illustrated in Fig. 2 (A-D) manifested by disappearance of the temporary drift of the basal line, i.e. stabilisation of the basal line. The data for $K_{Br/Cl}^{Pot}$ (Fig. 4) confirm the fact that the values of the selectivity coefficients of ISE depend both on the mode of calculation and on the conditions of the experiment. As seen from the figure, the same concentration of bromide ions in the flow carrier $K_{Br/Cl}^{Pot}$ assumes different values depending on bromide concentration in the calibrating solutions.

Fig. 4. $K_{Br/Cl}^{Pot}$ at constant chloride concentration in the sample (0.1 M Cl⁻) and variable bromide concentration, indicated on the abscissa. The flow carrier is a mixture of 0.7 M NaNO₃ and different Br⁻ additives (from 0 to 8.0 ppm) marked with figures on the respective curve.

The above facts clearly indicate that for determination of Br⁻ in presence of chloride ions, the addition of Br⁻ in the flow carrier exerts an influence in improving the selectivity and increasing the speed of analysis.

Presence of chloride in the flow carrier: An experiment was also conducted with addition of chloride ions in the flow carrier as recommended¹⁶ for elimination of the hindering chloride influence. However due to the high chloride concentration in the analytical object, it was necessary to add high concentration in the flow carrier as well. Ultimately, this proved to be inadequate. Even with 5 mM Cl⁻ in the flow carrier, an uninterrupted drift appeared on the basal line (Fig. 2E).

Final characteristics of the system: The above mentioned parameters were studied within wide limits (Table 1). In the last column of the Table, we see the values of these parameters which provide realisation of a relatively low sample dispersion $D=3.2$. In this way, a complete kinetic discrimination is achieved of the iodide ions and improvement of the selectivity of the bromide membrane in presence of chloride ions. Besides, the temporary drift of the electrode potential caused by high chloride concentration, is entirely eliminated. The system, so optimised, is characterised with a coefficient of variation of the analytical signal less than 1% and analysis of over 30 samples/h.

Supplement: The optimised flow injection system was applied for determination of Br⁻ in sea water. The calibration curves for all three cells used are

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL DATA OF BROMIDE IN SEA WATER AS COMPARED TO THE RECOMMENDED TITRIMETRIC METHOD*

Sample no.	Cell**	Bromide content (ppm)		Chloride in standard solution (M)
		PIP; $n=6$; $p=0.95$	Method*	
1	A	44.3+/-0.8	45.0	0.2
	B	44.9+/-0.9		
2	A	36.6+/-0.9	35.9	0.2
	B	36.2+/-0.8		
3	A	50.8+/-0.9	50.0	0.2
	B	51.0+/-1.0		
4	C	29.0+/-0.8	28.9	0.15

*Ref. 12. ** (A), Fig. 1b; (B), Fig. 1c; (C), 'wall jet' (Ref. 11).

linear. As this could be expected, the high chloride concentration exerts an essential influence on the gradient of the calibration curves. This low gradient (30% of the theoretical one) is compensated to a considerable degree by the high reproducibility of the analytical signal (Table 2). The results obtained from the suggested method are quite comparable to those of the recommended titrimetric method for determining Br^- in sea water^{1,2}.

References

1. A. GREKOVICH, D. MORACHEVSKY and V. JURINSKA, "Ionexchange and Ionometry", Leningrad, 1979, p. 222.
2. B. NIKOLSKII and E. MATEROVA, "Ion Selektivni Elektrodi", Chimia, Leningrad, 1980.
3. V. SAVENKO, *Okeanologiya*, 1976, **16**, 825.
4. L. ILCHEVA and R. YANAKIEV, *Comm. Department Chem., Bulg. Acad. Sci.*, 1990, **23**, 167.
5. R. CHRISTOVA, R. STEFANOVA and M. MEN, *Ann. Univ. Sofia*, 1973/1974, **68**, 109.
6. E. DUFFY and J. STUART, *Analyst*, 1975, **100**, 739.
7. A. KOZHDESTVENSKIY, "Hydrochemistry of the Bulgarian Sector of the Black Sea", Bulgarian Academy of Sciences publishing, Sofia, 1986, p. 122.
8. K. TOPE, J. FUCSKO, E. LINDNER, Z. FEHER and E. PUNGOR, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1988, **179**, 359.
9. K. CAMMANN, *Fresenius Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1988, **329**, 691.
10. W. FRENZEL, *Fresenius Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1988, **329**, 698.
11. W. FRENZEL, *Fresenius Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1987, **327**, 10.
12. "Methods of Sea Water Analysis", eds. K. GRASSHOFF, M. EHRHARDT and K. KREMLING, Verlag Chemie, 1983, p. 260.
13. L. ILCHEVA and K. CAMMANN, *Fresenius Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1985, **322**, 232.
14. L. ILCHEVA, M. TROJANOWICZ and T. KRAWCZYNSKI vel KRAWCZYK, *Fresenius Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1987, **328**, 27.
15. M. TROJANOWICZ and W. FRENZEL, *Fresenius Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1987, **328**, 653.
16. J. VAN STADEN, *Analyst*, 1987, **112**, 595.